

Information Engagement in Kerala's Old Age Homes; A Study on Elderly Preference to Children's Literature

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Abstract: *This study investigates the preference for children's literature among elderly residents in old age homes in Kerala, examining the emotional, cognitive, and social factors that contribute to this trend. The research focuses on two government-run old age homes in Kerala with functional libraries and a substantial collection of books. Fourteen elderly residents, identified as readers, were interviewed. Employing a qualitative approach, the interview transcripts were thematically analyzed using Braun and Clarke's (2006) method. The analysis revealed themes of nostalgia, emotional comfort, cognitive ease, and social interaction. These findings provide insights into the unique role of children's literature in enhancing the well-being of elderly individuals.*

Keywords: Children's Literature, Elderly, Old Age Homes, Nostalgia, Cognitive Ease, Social Interaction, Qualitative Research

Background

As an avid reader and a researcher deeply interested in the therapeutic benefits of literature, I have always been curious about how different age groups perceive books. This curiosity is rooted in my personal experiences with a beloved book, *The Little Prince*. When I first read it as a child, its enchanting narrative and whimsical illustrations captured my imagination. Revisiting it during my teenage years, adolescence, and youth, I noticed how my perceptions evolved, each reading offering new layers of meaning and insight. This personal journey sparked a broader interest in understanding how literature preferences change over time. I found myself increasingly drawn to children's literature and light-hearted stories as I grew older. Initially, I thought this was a unique quirk of mine, but during the course of my research, I discovered that many others share similar preferences. This realization led me to wonder how elderly individuals, particularly those in institutional settings, perceive children's literature.

As a doctoral candidate focusing on old age homes and its information engagement landscape, my curiosity about senior citizens' reading habits deepened. I wanted to explore how elderly residents in Kerala, a state renowned for its high literacy rates and progressive senior care policies, engage with children's literature. Prior to this, I conducted background research among older adults living with their

families, which provided valuable context for understanding the peculiarities of those in institutional settings.

Kerala, with the largest number of old age homes in India, presents a unique environment for this study. The state's rich literary culture and its emphasis on senior care create a fascinating backdrop for examining the cognitive and emotional impacts of reading children's literature among elderly residents. I aim to explore how these literary preferences affect their cognitive health and overall well-being, considering the influence of Kerala's cultural heritage and literary traditions on their reading habits. Through this research, I hope to uncover insights that can inform and enhance the quality of life for elderly individuals in old age homes.

Old Age Homes in Kerala

An old age home, also known as a nursing home, elderly care facility, or retirement home, is a place that provides food, clothing, shelter, and healthcare for elderly individuals. Although these homes may signify familial rejection, they also represent societal acceptance and care. Studies show that depression rates are higher among residents of old age homes, increasing with age (Goud & Nikhade, 2015). Kerala, with the highest proportion of elderly population in India, also has the most old age homes in the country (Beevi, 2010). There are 623 registered old age homes in Kerala, both government and private, with the largest numbers in Ernakulam and Thrissur districts (Raghnath, 2019).

Review of Literature

In the realm of children's literature, Nusaiba (2023) and Rundell (2023) have underscored its universal appeal, asserting that these books offer a sanctuary for adults burdened by their own biases and opinions. They serve as a beacon in moments of adult powerlessness, illuminating the path towards understanding and empathy. This unique genre of literature, often dismissed as simplistic, holds profound educational benefits. As Freeman, Feeney, and Moravcik's study (2011) emphasizes, children's literature promotes personal growth and increases appreciation for quality literature, serving as a bridge between the world of the reader and the broader universe of human experiences. The act of reading, particularly the habit of delving into children's books, is not merely a pastime. Merga's study (2017) underscores the diverse motivations behind maintaining regular reading habits, from knowledge acquisition and personal development to mental stimulation and escapism. It paints a picture of reading as a journey of discovery, a voyage that sails across the seas of knowledge and anchors at the island of wisdom. The benefits of reading extend beyond the cognitive realm. Antunes et al.'s research (2021) found that reading serves as a crucial tool for coping with difficulties and enhancing life quality throughout the aging process. It is a companion in solitude, a guide in confusion, and a solace in distress.

In the context of elder care institutions in India, the role of social capital is critical. Samanta and Gangopadhyay's study (2017) critically examines this role, underscoring the importance of understanding the cultural and social dynamics within these institutions. It highlights the need for a supportive and inclusive environment that fosters a sense of belonging and community among the elderly. Rajan's study (2002) provides a comprehensive overview of the old age home scenario in India, with a particular focus on Kerala. The state, known for its rich cultural heritage and progressive social policies, has a unique approach to elderly care. The study highlights the peculiarities of Kerala in elderly care and its significance, shedding light on the growing importance of old age homes in providing care for the elderly. Within the old age homes, shared reading groups have emerged as a

therapeutic intervention for older adults, particularly those with dementia and DeVries et al.'s study (2019) highlights the potential of these groups in improving engagement, social interaction, and cognitive skills. These groups serve as a platform for the elderly to connect with each other, share their experiences, and find comfort in the familiar narratives of children's literature. Poerio and Totterdell's study (2020) investigate the impact of fiction on the well-being of older adults. It concludes that personal engagement with the content of an audiobook can have a positive enduring impact on various aspects of well-being. This finding underscores the power of literature, particularly children's literature, in enhancing the quality of life for older adults, offering them a window to revisit their childhood, rekindle their imagination, and reignite their zest for life.

Problem Statement

Despite extensive research on the benefits of reading for the elderly, little is known about why some prefer children's literature specifically. This study seeks to fill that gap by exploring the emotional, cognitive, and social factors behind this preference.

Research Aim and Objectives

This research aims to explore why elderly residents in Kerala old age homes prefer children's literature. The objectives are:

1. To understand the emotional connections and nostalgic elements associated with children's literature.
2. To identify cognitive benefits and challenges that make children's literature more appealing than adult literature.
3. To explore social and cultural influences on reading preferences among the elderly.
4. To analyze the role of children's literature in the daily lives and well-being of elderly residents.

Significance

This study aims to provide insights that can inform the development of reading programs tailored for the elderly, enhancing their mental and emotional well-being.

Methodology

Research Design

In exploring why elderly residents in old age homes in Kerala preferred children's literature, I employed a qualitative, exploratory research design. This approach allowed for in-depth exploration of participants' personal experiences, perceptions, and the underlying reasons behind their literary preferences.

Participants

The study involved a purposive sample of 14 elderly residents from two government old age homes across Kerala with functional libraries with substantial collection of books. Participants were selected based on specific criteria: they were aged 60 or older, regularly engaged in reading activities, and were willing to participate in in-depth interviews. This sample size was intended to gather a diverse range of experiences and perspectives while reaching data saturation, where new interviews no longer yielded new insights.

Data Collection

To gain a comprehensive understanding of the participants' experiences and views, semi-structured interviews were conducted. This flexible format enabled thorough exploration of their stories. The interview guide included open-ended questions aimed at eliciting detailed responses about their reading habits, preferences for children's literature, and the emotional, cognitive, and social impacts of these reading choices. Key questions included:

1. Could you describe your favourite types of books to read?
2. What drew you to children's literature specifically?
3. How did reading children's literature make you feel?
4. Did you notice any changes in your mood or cognitive abilities related to reading these books?
5. Could you share any specific memories or experiences related to reading children's literature?

Interviews were conducted in the participants' native language, with each session lasting approximately 45 to 60 minutes. With participants' consent, all interviews were translated, back-translated, and transcribed verbatim for analysis.

Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using thematic analysis, specifically employing Braun and Clarke's (2006) approach, to identify recurring themes and patterns related to the preference for children's literature. The process involved familiarization by reading and re-reading transcripts to become thoroughly immersed in the data. Initial codes were generated to identify significant features of the data, which were then grouped into potential themes. These themes were reviewed for accuracy, refined, and named to capture their essence. Data saturation was confirmed and a detailed report was written, including four illustrative verbatim quotes from the participants to support each objective.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval and study order were obtained from the relevant ministry review board. Informed consent was secured from all participants, ensuring they understood the study's purpose, procedures, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. Confidentiality was maintained by anonymizing all data and securely storing the transcripts.

Results

Objective 1: Emotional Connections and Nostalgia

"I've always had a soft spot for children's books. They remind me of my grandchildren and the stories I used to read to them. In my childhood, our household had a large book collection and we used to buy weekly magazines. There were more than 10 children in every house back then, not just 2-3 like nowadays. We used to fight over who would read the children's section first. It brings back memories of my own childhood and the joy of imagination. Reading these books makes me feel young again, reminiscing about those special moments with my family. It's comforting, like revisiting cherished memories."

"I love all kinds of children's comics. Do you know Balarama, Balabhumi, and Poombatta (children's weeklies in Malayalam)? I don't get to read them here because they don't have a subscription and I don't even know if it is as good as those times. But at the house where I worked as a maid, I used to read them like crazy when the children went to school. Sometimes I even borrowed them to take home.

It was perhaps the best part of my day, helping me forget about my daily worries. I still remember all those characters; they are forever living in my mind. And I really want to read more of those.”

Figure 1: Popular Malayalam Children’s Magazine Poombatta from 1979

(Source: <https://www.techtraveleat.com/poombatta-masika/>)

1. “There is this one book in the library here that I read the other day, I forgot its name. But it was a very good book about a boy and his pet goat. I teared up reading that. When we were young, we didn’t have much money. There were many of us living in a house. We had a goat, and my elder sister and I were very fond of it. It was a happy day when it gave birth to two kids. Then, one day, our father had to sell them for money, and my sister and I cried like anything. Ah, this story brought all those memories back.”
2. “I like reading Kunjunni Mashu's works. They are funny and many of the stories are so relatable. And Sumangala’s books, too. It's almost as if you can feel and smell everything around you. The way of narration is from old times, not modern, which I really enjoy. There are a number of books like these here, and I've already read them all.”

Figure 2: Malayalam Writer Kunjunni

(Source:

[https://archives.mathrubhumi.com/image/contentid/policy:1.5732731:1645044027/image.jpg?\\$p=0f6e831&f=16x10&w=852&q=0.8](https://archives.mathrubhumi.com/image/contentid/policy:1.5732731:1645044027/image.jpg?$p=0f6e831&f=16x10&w=852&q=0.8))

1. **Nostalgia and Childhood Memories:**

1. Participants recall fond memories from their childhood associated with children's books and comics.
2. **Example:** "They remind me of my grandchildren and the stories I used to read to them. It brings back memories of my own childhood and the joy of imagination."

2. **Longing for Past Reading Experiences:**

1. There is a strong desire to relive past reading experiences, particularly related to specific books and comics that were cherished in the past.
2. **Example:** "I really want to read more of those [children's comics]."

3. **Emotional Impact of Stories:**

1. Certain stories evoke strong emotional reactions, bringing back memories and sometimes leading to tears.
2. **Example:** "There was a very good book about a boy and his pet goat. I teared up reading that."

4. **Appreciation for Specific Authors and Narratives:**

1. Participants appreciate specific authors and narratives that are reminiscent of older times and evoke a sense of familiarity.
2. **Example:** "I like reading Kunjuni Mashu's works. They are funny and many of the stories are so relatable."

5. **Connection to Family and Home:**

- i) Books and comics are closely tied to memories of family and home, including reading together with siblings.
- ii) **Example:** "It was a happy day when [the goat] gave birth to two kids. Then, one day, our father had to sell them for money, and my sister and I cried like anything."

Objective 2: Cognitive Benefits and Challenges

"I find children's literature easier to understand than dense novels. They keep my mind engaged without the strain. There was a time when I used to read all those serious books out there, but these days I can't even process them. I can't give my focus towards those kinds of books anymore. Even if I tried, I will not be finishing it. Few pages and that's it. But I can read children's books effortlessly."

"In a way, it reminds me of many things that I tend to forget. Whenever I'm reading a book from this genre, it's like a time travel ride and a happy one. I pay attention to the details, the nuances, and all those colours and illustrations. It keeps me fresh and clear-headed."

"The kind of imagination I get to see and read in children's literature is what hooks me to it. There are certain things I don't understand that well, yet I've realized I have a creative part in my head, and these days I've started to imagine things and it's all colourful. When I was a child, I never found books of this sort. These are quite good, and there are some strange ideas in them. This old age home has a good collection."

"Have you read the book 'Albhutaneerali'? It's a book written by K V Ramanathan. It's so interesting. Every time I read it, it's like a new world has been opened. There are a lot of things I don't really

understand, scientific terms and all, but the book is interesting and thrilling. And there's another writer, Sivadas, his books are also like this—very informative, imaginative, and scientific.”

Figure 3: *Albhutha Neerali*, by K V Ramanathan, a popular science fiction for Children in Malayalam

(Source: <https://www.goodreads.com/book/show/17661995-albhutha-neerali>)

- **Ease of Understanding and Cognitive Engagement:**

- a. Participants find children's literature easier to understand and mentally engaging compared to more complex novels.
- b. **Example:** "I find children's literature easier to understand than dense novels. They keep my mind engaged without the strain."

- **Stimulation of Imagination:**

- Reading children's literature stimulates participants' imagination and creative thinking.
- **Example:** "The kind of imagination I get to see and read in children's literature is what hooks me to it."

- **Interest in Informative and Scientific Content:**

- a. Some participants express interest in children's literature that includes informative and scientific content.
- b. **Example:** "Have you read the book 'Albhuthaneerali'? It's so interesting ... very informative, imaginative, and scientific."

Objective 3: Social and Cultural Influences

“These days I don't know if the children know how our Onam and Vishu used to be. It is good that these books exist. At least by reading these, they get to know and feel it. I read a storybook a couple of days ago, and there was a story about Onam and its festivities. I was so happy to see that some of those things I have grown up with are written there in a nice way.”

“Most of the children’s books I have read are of some translations. I think it is a Malayali thing, we are drawn to experience and know about other cultures. That is why, we migrate and travel more than others. During my youth, I have also travelled to some places I have read only in the books. Now I am not even in a condition to walk. But I love reading Ruskin Bond, Tom Sawyer, books of that sort. The way you can travel and experience all that just by sitting in a room and reading it.”

“The moral lessons and simplicity of children's stories are what draw me to them. Aesoppu kathakal (Aesop’s fables) is a book I hold dear. It reminds me of the values my grandparents, and the bible taught me. Reading these books in Malayalam takes me back to my childhood. The stories might be different, but the values are all same everywhere in the world.”

“I love reading Puranas, back when I was with family I used to read all those Amarchitra katha books where they will be featuring the stories from Ramayana, Mahabharata and all. It is good you know, easy to understand, and that too with pictures. Here, there are a number of Purana books in the library. And I love reading if it is Kuttikalude (Children’s). Yesterday, I was reading the story of Bali.”

Figure 4: Amarchithra Katha Featuring a tale from Mahabharata

(Source: <https://comicsbyaroonkalandy.blogspot.com/2016/07/vintage-malayalam-comics.html>)

- **Preservation and Sharing of Cultural Traditions:**
- Participants value children's books that preserve and share cultural traditions and stories.
- **Example:** "These days I don't know if the children know how our Onam and Vishu used to be. It is good that these books exist."
- **Appreciation for Moral and Simple Stories:**
 - Participants appreciate the moral lessons and simplicity of children's stories.
 - **Example:** "The moral lessons and simplicity of children's stories are what draw me to them."

Objective 4: Role in Daily Lives and Well-being

“My life has become quite monotonous since coming here. There is actually nothing much to do. Earlier, I used to take part in a couple of activities like yoga and board games. I am not healthy anymore. These days, all I have are these books. Reading is my only activity, and it is helping. I am reading simple things: children's books and stories. I don't know how to say this, but reading keeps me alive.”

“The only visitors we have are kids from schools and colleges. Last time, some of them asked me to tell a story, and they really liked it. They said they would come again. I told them a story from the Puranas. The morals and teachings of the Puranas, I don't think any books these days convey that. I am reading children's books to understand their simplicity and ease of understanding. I have this thought in my head that I will write some Purana stories for children. Just a thought, something to keep me busy. I am actually scribbling things and trying to remember how the stories made me feel so that I can do the same.”

“If I sit and do nothing, my mind gets clouded with all the things that have happened to me in the past, and I end up crying. TV doesn't help. Not so long ago, I started reading the books in the library. I can't understand the complicated books. Children's books are my thing. They are funny and feel-good.”

“It's actually hilarious how I ended up reading only light-hearted material these days. I used to be active in politics, and all my life, the kind of material I read was serious and political. I can't even look at that stuff now. I mean the serious stuff. I am more comfortable with Bobanum Moliyum than Marx nowadays.”

Figure 5: Bobanum Moliyum Comics by Toms

(Source: <https://www.thenewsminute.com/kerala/bobanum-moliyum-how-two-naughty-kids-inspired-iconic-malayalam-comic-139244>)

▪ Role in Daily Life:

- For many participants, reading children's books plays a significant role in their daily lives, providing entertainment and mental stimulation.

- **Example:** "Reading is my only activity, and it is helping. I am reading simple things: children's books and stories."

- **Potential for Social Engagement and Creativity:**

- Children's books provide opportunities for social engagement and creativity.
- **Example:** "Last time, some of them [children] asked me to tell a story, and they really liked it. ... I have this thought in my head that I will write some Purana stories for children."

Discussion

The study aimed to understand why elderly individuals in old age homes in Kerala tend to prefer children's literature as they age. The findings reveal several key insights into this phenomenon. Several themes were emerged from the thematic analysis of the interview transcripts (Figure 6). Participants frequently reminisced about childhood memories associated with reading, indicating a strong sense of nostalgia. Children's literature was often remembered for its simplicity and moral teachings, which participants found comforting and reassuring in their later years (Freeman, Feeney, & Moravcik, 2011). This nostalgia was deeply intertwined with emotional connections to family, home, and cultural traditions, highlighting the enduring impact of childhood reading experiences on elderly individuals (Nusaiba, 2023; Rundell, 2023). In terms of cognitive benefits, children's literature was found to be easier to understand and engage with compared to more complex adult literature. Participants reported that children's stories stimulate their imagination, provide moments of escape, and offer valuable life lessons (Merga, 2017). The simplicity of children's literature was noted as a relief from the cognitive challenges they may face with more demanding texts (DeVries et al., 2019).

Figure 6: Themes Emerged from Thematic Analysis

Socially, children's literature fosters a sense of community and belonging among elderly residents in old age homes. Shared readings and discussions about children's stories create opportunities for social engagement and interaction, enhancing their overall well-being (Samanta & Gangopadhyay, 2017).

This communal aspect of reading is particularly important in the context of old age homes, where social connections can significantly impact the quality of life (Poerio & Totterdell, 2020).

Conclusion

The preference for children's literature among elderly individuals in old age homes in Kerala appears to be driven by a combination of emotional, cognitive, and social factors. Nostalgia plays a central role, as participants cherish childhood memories associated with these stories. The simplicity and moral teachings of children's literature provide comfort and cognitive stimulation while also facilitating social connections within the community.

Understanding these motivations can inform strategies to promote reading and improve the quality of life for elderly individuals in old age homes. Encouraging access to children's literature and facilitating reading groups could provide meaningful opportunities for emotional expression, cognitive engagement, and social interaction.

Suggestions

Based on the findings, several suggestions can be made for caregivers, policymakers, and health professionals working with elderly populations in old age homes:

1. **Promote Access to Children's Literature:** Ensure that old age homes have a variety of children's books available for residents to read and share.
2. **Facilitate Reading Groups:** Organize reading groups focused on children's literature to encourage social interaction and discussion.
3. **Educational Programs:** Offer educational programs that explore the benefits of children's literature and its role in emotional and cognitive well-being.

Limitations

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting the findings of this study:

1. **Sample Specificity:** The study focused on elderly individuals in two old age homes in Kerala, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other populations or settings.
2. **Self-Reporting Bias:** The study relied on self-reported data, which may introduce biases related to social desirability or memory recall.

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